

Transport Number of Cadmium and Iodide in Aqueous Solution of Cadmium Iodide by Analytical Boundary Method

D. Mangaraj* and S. Aditya**

Transport number of cadmium ion in cadmium iodide solution, by following the cation boundary in the analytical boundary method, increases from 0.308 to 0.438 as the concentration increases from 0.02 to 0.05*N* and then decreases to 0.124 at 0.5*N*. The iodide transport number from the anion boundary studies increases from 0.548 to 0.90 as the concentration increases from 0.02 to 0.4*N*. Transport number measurements, using Hittorf's method at 30°, compare favourably with the values obtained by the anion boundary studies. The increase in iodide transport number and the decrease in cadmium transport number may be explained on the basis of the formation of positively and negatively charged complexes at different concentrations of cadmium iodide.

Behaviour of cadmium iodide in aqueous solution has been the subject of long and extensive study. The abnormal transport numbers, determined by Redlich¹ and subsequently confirmed by Longworth², are explained on the basis that cadmium iodide forms auto-complexes of the type $Cd(CdI_4)$ which in aqueous solution dissociates into Cd^{2+} and $(CdI_4)^{2-}$ ions. Subsequently it was shown³ that the activity coefficient of cadmium ion in aqueous solution of cadmium iodide was very low and comparable to that of weak electrolytes. Studies of Raman spectra⁴ indicated the presence of species containing bands in aqueous solutions of cadmium iodide. Leden⁵ considered the existence of both positively and negatively charged complexes like CdI^+ , CdI_3^- , and CdI_4^{2-} and calculated the association constants. Similar results have been obtained by Alberty and King⁶ by measuring the cation and anion mobilities at different ratios of cadmium and iodide ions.

In our previous communication⁷ it has been shown that transport number measurements by analytical boundary method can be successfully applied to detect the existence of positively charged complex species like $Pb(NO_3)^+$ and $Cd(NO_3)^+$ in aqueous solutions of their nitrates. Since cadmium iodide solution contains both positively and negatively charged complexes, a study of its transport number by analytical boundary method, using both cation and anion boundaries, may be interesting.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used for transport number measurements by analytical boundary method was of the type described previously⁷. Extra pure metallic cadmium was used as

*Present address: Department of Applied Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur.

**Department of Applied Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-9.

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3. Robinson and Wilson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 738.
4. Delwells *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1938, 208, 184.
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cathode and platinum foil as anode in the anion boundary experiments and metallic cadmium cathode and anode in cation boundary experiments. An electronic voltage regulator was used to cut down fluctuations of the supply voltage. Both silver and iodine coulometers were used for ascertaining total quantity of electricity passed.

The apparatus for transport number measurements by Hittorf's method was the same as described earlier⁸. The connecting limbs were made stout to compensate the effect of smaller conductance of cadmium iodide solution.

Stock solutions of cadmium iodide were prepared by dissolving cadmium iodide (E. Merck, extra pure) crystals in doubly distilled water and standardised gravimetrically by 8-hydroxyquinoline method. Stock solutions of cadmium perchlorate were prepared by dissolving extra pure cadmium carbonate in perchloric acid (A.R.) and standardised in the above manner. Ferric chloride and ferric perchlorate solutions were prepared by dissolving freshly prepared ferric hydroxide in HCl (extra pure) and perchloric acid (extra pure) respectively. Potassium iodide used was of E. Merck, extra pure quality and potassium chloride of E. Merck, G. R. quality.

In cation-boundary experiments potassium chloride solution was introduced between potassium iodide and ferric chloride solutions to avoid their interaction. Concentrations of indicator solutions were adjusted by following Kohlrausch's relation⁹. In each series, experiments were done also with higher and lower concentrations of the indicator to be sure that the one used was in the plateau region. About 12 to 15 mA of current was passed for two hours in each run. All experiments were carried out at room temperature ($30^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$).

In anion-boundary experiments, the solutions in the indicator compartment were estimated as silver iodide and in cation-boundary experiments, the amount of cadmium by 8-hydroxyquinoline method. In Hittorf's experiments, cadmium in both cathode and anode compartments was analysed.

Three to four runs were taken at each concentration. The average values of transport number, measured along with maximum discrepancies in each case, are recorded in

TABLE I

Transport number of cadmium and iodide ions in solution of cadmium iodide at $30^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$.

Conc.	Anion boundary.		Cation boundary.		$\frac{1}{2}t_{Cd^{+2}}$		
	No. of runs.	t_i^- .	No. of runs.	$\frac{1}{2}t_{Cd^{+2}}$	Hittorf's method.	Redlich.	Longworth
0.02 N	3	0.548 ± 0.01	3	0.398 ± 0.01	..	..	..
0.05	3	0.560 ± 0.01	3	0.438 ± 0.01	0.428 ± 0.08	0.410	0.400
0.10	4	0.650 ± 0.005	3	0.375 ± 0.002	0.325 ± 0.02	0.301	0.301
0.20	4	0.755 ± 0.012	3	0.303 ± 0.013	0.241 ± 0.02	0.197	0.180
0.30	..	..	..	..	..	0.050	0.010
0.40	5	0.900 ± 0.02	..	..	..	..	..
0.50	..	..	3	0.124 ± 0.004	..	0.003	0.000

8. Managarej *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 217.

9. Spiro and Patron, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, 478, 263.

The present results differ from those by Redlich¹ and Longworth² (their data have been shown in columns 7 and 8 in Table I). So by way of check, some transport number measurements at 30° by Hittorf's method have been taken. These results (given in column 6 of the table) compare fairly well with the numbers obtained by analytical boundary studies, but are higher than those of both Redlich and Longworth. This is possibly because the temperature is higher in the present case. The variation of transport number with concentration is, however, of the same order and is expected in the case of cadmium iodide which is known to form complexes in solution.

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MAYURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
REVENSHAW COLLEGE,
CUTTACK-3.

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